

**NEW APPROACHES TO THE PHYSIOLOGICAL JUSTIFICATION OF
THE GAMING METHOD AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ITS
APPLICATION IN COMPETITIVE ACTIVITIES**

Tashpulatov K.D

student of group BB 01-21,

Abatova G.N.

teacher

e:mail- gulzaraabatova@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada o'yin usulining fiziologik asoslanishi va uni raqobatbardosh faoliyatda qo'llash samaradorligi ko'zda tutilgan, jismoniy faoliyatning tolerantligi va joizligi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar tananing individual yosh bosqichlarida moslashish qobiliyatini, fiziologik tizimlarning funktsional etukligi darajasini, rivojlanish darajasini hisobga olgan holda zarur va yo'naltirilgan mashg'ulotlar jarayonida vosita imkoniyatlarini takomillashtirish.

Kalit so'zlar: tana, anatomiya, fiziologiya, tibbiy-biologik, pedagogik, jismoniy madaniyat, tarbiya, basketbol, jismoniy tayyorgarlik

Аннотация : в данной статье предусматривает физиологического обоснования игрового метода и эффективности его применения в соревновательной деятельности, необходимы данные о переносимости и допустимости физических нагрузок с учетом адаптационных возможностей организма на отдельных возрастных этапах, о степени функциональной зрелости физиологических систем, об уровнях развития и совершенствования двигательных возможностей в процессе направленной тренировки.

Ключевые слова: организм, анатомия, физиология, медико-биологические, педагогические, физической культуры, воспитания, basketbol, физическая подготовка

The relevance of the work - Biomedical and pedagogical sciences deal with man as a being not only biological, but also social. The socio-biological foundations of physical culture are the principles of interaction of social and biological patterns in the process of mastering the values of physical culture by a person.

The natural science foundations of physical culture are a complex of biomedical sciences (anatomy, physiology, biology, biochemistry, hygiene, etc.). Anatomy and physiology are the most important biological sciences about the structure and functions of the human body. Man obeys the biological laws inherent in all living beings. However, it differs from representatives of the animal world not only in its structure, but also in its developed thinking, intelligence, speech, features of social and living conditions and social relationships. Labor and the influence of the social environment in the process of human development have influenced the biological characteristics of the modern human body and its environment.

The formation of basic motor qualities and skills in the process of physical education can be more successful provided that the means and methods of physical culture are reasonably used, as well as the intensification of physical exertion requiring strenuous activity of all physiological systems.

The purpose and objectives of the study - to show the importance of the physiological justification of the gaming method and the effectiveness of its application in competitive activities.

Research objectives - to make it clear that in any gaming methods, the physical activity used will have a health-improving value, and will be effective only if a scientific physiological approach is used.

The task of the study - to identify the effectiveness of the use of various physiological properties in gaming methods.

The research method - analysis of the experiment of rationing physical activity based on theoretical data with subsequent conclusions.

In the process of general physical training, the following tasks are solved: education of basic physical qualities, improvement of functional capabilities,

expansion of motor skills, improvement of athletic performance, versatile physical development, stimulation of recovery processes, health promotion.

For these purposes, a set of general physical exercises is used, thereby creating the basis for the specialized development of individual qualities. Different types of exercises cause faster adaptation and accelerate the course of recovery processes.

Dexterity- It is of great importance in all kinds of sports, but it becomes especially important in those that are characterized by complex techniques and continuously changing conditions. The definition of dexterity as a physical quality presents significant difficulties for a specialist. This is due to the fact that the question is not entirely clear - how dexterity can be measured. The main measurement of dexterity is considered to be the coordination complexity of the action, the accuracy of execution and the execution time.

Flexibility – this is understood as the properties of the musculoskeletal system, which determine the degree of mobility of its links. There is an active one that manifests itself due to its own muscular efforts and a passive one that manifests itself when external forces are applied to a moving part of the body – gravity, partner's efforts. Passive flexibility is always greater than active flexibility, and in most cases its increase creates prerequisites for an increase in the amplitude of active movements.

Special endurance – gaming – is mainly provided by a mixed character - aerobic-anaerobic. For its improvement, it requires quite long exercises of up to 150 minutes of variable nature with high and maximum intensity – such a mode of operation in cross-country running over heavily rough terrain and running with alternating speeds, in mobile and sports games.

Special speed. In basketball, the success of sports actions is determined by the speed of simple and complex motor reactions, the time of the speed of movement of single movements in actions related to the speed of response to the external situation of the model of the upcoming movement – the readiness potential – which allows you to prepare the control mechanisms in advance of events and thereby reduce the time of implementation of the motor action.

Special strength training. The power ability, which is directly manifested in the magnitude of the working, motor effort, is provided by the holistic reaction of the body associated with the mobilization of mental qualities of the functions of the motor, muscular and other physiological systems.

Explosive power . In conditions of sports activity, it manifests itself in isometric and dynamic modes of muscle work, and in the latter condition – overcoming various external resistance in magnitude.

High-speed force manifests itself in conditions of high-speed movements against relatively small external resistance and is provided by such properties of maximum effort that determine the starting and accelerating muscle strength.

SFP tools and methods. The means of SFP include exercises that, firstly, correspond to a competitive exercise according to the mode of operation of the body: secondly, they contain training effects in order to increase the level of functionality that the body is already equipped with, thirdly, they provide the necessary energy base for improving technical and tactical skills.

Game training is an integral form of sports training for basketball players.

It is aimed at improving the skills of fighting. The main means of game preparation is a two-way training game specially organized and managed by a coach. The main task of basketball players in an educational game is not so much to achieve results, as to master the ability to fight, observe the course of the game, distinguishing the important and essential from the accidental and secondary.

The tasks of the game method:

1. Improving the ability to distribute forces, which involves the formation of skills to maximize your strength and capabilities, combine periods of intense motor activity and relaxation.

2. Improvement of individual actions and interactions with teammates, which is embodied in the implementation of the developed game plan or operational tasks of the coach.

3. Improvement in the use of mastered tactical systems, combinations and their variants.

To manage the game preparation, it is recommended to somewhat facilitate the playing conditions when performing control tasks, artificially limit time and space, increase competitive difficulties, use confounding factors, systematically quantitatively and qualitatively monitor the performance of basketball players in game tasks

To increase the effectiveness of the game method, it is advisable to use a set of methodological techniques:

1. Include in the educational game tasks related to the mandatory implementation of the chosen scheme of playing the game or a planned system of interactions to overcome confounding factors.

2. Conduct a training game with partners acting according to the likely tactical plan of future main opponents.

3. To give specific tasks to athletes that help solve a team-wide game task.

4. Periodically introduce players from the reserve into the main team, requiring them to clearly perform the received tactical task.

5. Use switching from one tactical combination and options to another according to predetermined signals.

6. Resort to sudden changes in the game environment for those involved, requiring a quick switch. Unexpected changes in the situation or the sudden use of a new tactical system by the enemy are difficult enough to quickly switch players and require targeted training. In an educational game, you should use a certain methodical sequence of complications, surprises, to improve players in switching. For this purpose, unexpected tactical interactions are used, which cause the transition to recently mastered techniques that have not yet been fully put into practice.

7. Use the final effort. This technique is aimed at forming the ability of those involved to give their best in the decisive moments of the match, quickly mobilize their

forces again and repeatedly repeat the maximum effort to consolidate the advantage achieved.

8. Consistently introduce rested players into the game.

9. Organize the participation of students in training competitions based on shortened and extended game modes. This game method is best used to form the skills to enter the game at any time and act for the benefit of the team.

The results of the study provide practically significant information that can be used during lessons and training in a secondary school in order to improve playing techniques, and in the future successfully apply them in competitions.

There were two main tasks in the work:

1. Using the data from the available literature, select methodological techniques and exercises that could be included in the training program aimed at improving the game preparation of schoolchildren engaged in basketball at school in sectional classes.

2. To test the effectiveness of the developed program in a comparative experiment on schoolchildren playing basketball in one of the secondary schools.

The group consisted of schoolchildren engaged in basketball and did not differ significantly in age, height, weight and playing data. Training sessions in this group were also held 3 times a week for 90 minutes each.

The training work of schoolchildren involved in basketball in KG contributed to some improvement in the initial data. During the three months of training, which took place at the same time as in the experimental group, there were some changes in the controlled parameters. Thus, the speed potential utilization rate when running backwards for 6 m changed by 1.62%, the speed utilization rate when moving sideways forward for 3 m increased by 2.33%, and the speed potential utilization rate when running backwards for 20 m improved by 2.65%, when running face forward by 2.96%. Measurements of back-to-front running time at 3 m also indicate positive shifts found in KG. This indicator improved by 5% over the three-month training period. The indicator for 3 m face forward improved by 2.81%, sideways forward by 6 m also

improved by 3.26%, the indicator for running face forward by 6 m improved by 2.21%, while running sideways forward by 20 m there was an improvement of 2.99%.

DISTANCES IN (M)	DATA FROM THE BEGINNING OF THE EXPERIMENT	EG In SEC.	EG In SEC.
BACKWARDS FOR 3M	2,2	2,06	2,09
SIDEWAYS FORWARD BY 3M	1,9	1,72	1,85
FACE FORWARD AT 3M	1,5	1,42	1,45
BACKWARDS FOR 6M	2,7	2,56	2,65
SIDEWAYS FORWARD BY 6M	2,5	2,37	2,41
FACE FORWARD AT 6M	2,1	1,98	2,05
BACKWARDS FOR 20M	6,3	5,93	6,13
SIDEWAYS FORWARD BY 20M	6,1	5,6	5,91
FACE FORWARD AT 20 M	4,2	3,99	4,07

The developed training program with a large application of the game method, as mentioned earlier, has already greatly contributed to the improvement of speed and strength qualities, speed of movement, all this proves the indicator in competitive

activity. Of the 13 games played by EEG, only 5 games were lost, while KG of the 13 games played lost 10 games, all games were played away. It is safe to say that our program has improved not only the speed and strength qualities that we have already seen earlier in the table, but also in competitive practice we also see a significant superiority over KG.

Classification by Farfel:

MOVEMENTS:

I. Stereotypical (standard) movements

1) Qualitative value (with a score in points).

2) Quantitative value (with an estimate in kg, meters, seconds).

Cyclic by power zones: maximum (10-30 s), submaximal (30c-5 min), large (5-30 min), moderate (30 min to several hours).

Acyclic: actually-power, speed-power, aiming.

II. Situational (non-standard) movements: sports games.

Non-standard or situational movements include sports games. These movements are characterized by: variable power of work, variability of the situation with a shortage of time.

Conclusions and suggestions

1. The study of the adaptation of physiological systems to physical loads of different capacities in school-age children is of great importance for understanding the age-sex patterns of the functioning of regulatory systems in muscular activity and the normalization of loads. As a result of a comprehensive study, it was possible to find out and identify age-related features of a number of adaptive reactions of the motor system, central and regional blood circulation and respiration, which ensure an increase in the process of individual development of human physical performance.

2. In the period from 15-16 years, the functional capabilities of the motor apparatus increase significantly. This is evidenced by an increase in the power and volume of the loads performed, an increase in the maximum rate of movement, the

maximum duration of work, and rapid recovery after loads of the functional state of the neuromotor apparatus.

3. It was noted that with a decrease in intensity, but simultaneously with an increase in the time of physical activity and the amount of work, the period of restoration of the functional state of the neuromuscular apparatus increases in boys and girls. An analysis of the indicators of central hemodynamics during physical work indicates that in all the studied children, with increasing load capacity, there is an increase in the IOC, which reaches its maximum values at 50% load and changes slightly with further increase in work capacity. In boys aged 14-16, the heart rate increases evenly from 20 to 50% of the load. Their pulse reaches high values when performing moderate intensity loads by the age of 15-16.

4. The peculiarities of the coordination structure and regulation of movements predetermined the methodological approach to the normalization of the corresponding exercises. The normalization of loads during exercises such as walking and running is usually based on the optimization of energy supply processes and oxygen regime processes. The factors limiting the load for exercises of this type are the development of hypoxia and processes that make it difficult to deliver oxygen and energy-rich substances to the place of their consumption in the body. According to these physiological parameters, walking and running loads are classified depending on age. With such rationing, the use of a heart rate indicator is acceptable. To normalize cyclic exercises used in a physical education lesson, it is important to highlight such moderately strenuous muscle activity that can be maintained for a long time without a significant increase in oxygen debt. The load of 50% of the maximum can be maintained for a long time. To assess the effect of physical activity on the body at 15-16 years of age, you can use the classification of loads, which includes 5 zones:

1. Low intensity zone (20-30%).

The work can be done here for a very long time. At the same time, all physiological functions of the body do not experience tension, the heart rate does not

exceed 100-120 beats / min. This includes low-intensity and low-speed exercise modes (walking, cycling, skiing, etc.)

2. Moderate intensity zone (50% of the maximum load).

The exercise regime in this area contributes to the development of overall endurance. The pulse rate when performing loads reaches 130-160 beats / min. Working in this zone helps to establish interaction between the functions of the cardiovascular system, respiration and the motor apparatus.

3. High intensity zone (70%).

It causes tension of physiological functions in the body of schoolchildren during muscular work. The performance of the load in this zone does not exceed 4-5 minutes for younger students, and 10 minutes for older ones.

4. The zone of submaximal or high intensity (80%).

It corresponds to the exercise regime (short-distance running, speed-strength exercises, static loads, etc.), in which the work of muscles, heart, etc. Organs and tissues are provided mainly by anaerobic energy sources. The maximum duration of cyclic loads for younger students is 50 s., and for older students – 1 min. and more.

5. Maximum intensity zone (100%).

It corresponds to the performance of physical exercises with maximum speed, maximum pace and an increase in the maximum time for performing loads up to 10 seconds. In such a short time, the functional shifts of the cardiovascular system, respiration and other functions do not reach high values.

5. In a state of relative physical rest, the heart rate gradually decreases with age, and the heart rate, on the contrary, increases. A significant shift towards an increase in blood UO occurs by the age of 14-15.

6. Students of the EG of the 10th grade have significantly more UO than in KG. It is obvious that due to the opposite age dynamics of heart rate and heart rate in a state of relative physical rest at the age of 13-17 years increases slightly. Schoolchildren have fewer KG of IOC than their peers FROM EG.

7. Education of basic physical qualities, improvement of functional capabilities, expansion of motor skills, improvement of athletic performance, versatile physical development, stimulation of recovery processes, health promotion, all these processes have become a reality thanks to our developed program.

8. I can say with confidence that this work will help to improve physical and functional condition, and will help to fight and win competitions more successfully.

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